

The Autobiography of Adad-guppi

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The Adad-guppi inscription is a rare pseudo-autobiography of a woman with political and religious power in the ancient Near East. Two copies of the inscription were discovered: one poorly preserved text excavated in 1907 at the archaeological site of Harran in southern Turkey, and another more complete copy discovered in 1958 as a part of the pavement steps to the Great Mosque at Harran. The text, written in Neo-Babylonian Cuneiform dating to the sixth century BCE, celebrates Adad-guppi's devotion to the gods, her service to the royal court and her role as queen mother to her son Nabonidus, the last king of Babylon. The monument stood in the ancient city of Harran in the moon god temple, named the Ehulhul, which was newly rebuilt by Nabonidus following its destruction during the Assyrian and Babylonian battle for power in the late seventh century BCE. Although the inscription is written as a first-person account by Adad-guppi, the emphasis on Nabonidus's right to kingship and the details of Adad-guppi's funeral support that it was created by someone in the royal court following Adad-guppi's death. The nature of the text is apologetic, seeking to justify the kingship of Adad-guppi's son Nabonidus, who ascended the throne despite his questionable royal lineage. According to the inscription, Adad-guppi was born in the reign of Assyrian king Ashurbanipal (649 BCE) and died during reign of her son Nabonidus (547 BCE). This would make her an astonishing 104 years old, which is about 70 years past life expectancy during that time. While it is not mentioned in this text, other sources tell us that her husband was a court servant named Nabu-balastu-iqi. Following the fall of Assyria in 609 BCE, Adad-guppi served in the Neo-Babylonian royal court and became queen mother during the tumultuous reign of Nabonidus. The inscription claims that Adad-guppi and Nabonidus respectfully served Babylonian kings Nabopolassar, Nebuchadnezzar, and Neriglissar and made gracious funerary offerings upon each of their deaths because their close kin did not perform the necessary rites for their deceased relatives. The assertion that those with familial claim to the throne did not exhibit piety to gods or kings is in contrast to Nabonidus's devoutness that eventually rewarded him with kingship over Babylon's irreverent legitimate heirs. Historical sources describe how Nabonidus usurped the throne from Babylonian king Labashi-Marduk in 556 BCE just a month into his reign. By his and his mother's own accounts, Nabonidus was not the next in line for the throne, but the inscription stresses that their devotion to the moon god landed him the position. Nabonidus was strong enough to maintain his position as ruler for sixteen years until 539 BCE when the Achaemenid Persians annexed the Babylonian empire. The text notably favors the moon god Sin calling him the "king of the gods," which is a departure from the exultation of Marduk, the traditional Babylonian chief deity. While the heartland of the Babylonian empire was in lower Mesopotamia, this text focuses on the city of Harran and the Ehulhul. It was not unlike Nabonidus to favor a city outside of Babylon as he did by living in Tayma, an oasis in the Saudi Arabian desert, for ten years during his reign. The destruction of Harran is framed as a consequence of Sin leaving the city in anger, and Adad-guppi's pious pleading was meant to entice Sin back to his residence in Harran just as it had secured her son's kingship. Because of Adad-guppi's devotion to the gods, she did not suffer any ailments that often come with old age, stating that her eyesight, limbs, appetite, and heart remained in good condition, and she witnessed four generations of her descendants. Of these descendants, we are aware of Nabonidus, king of Babylon, and his two children, Belshazzar the crown prince, and Ennigaldi, high priestess of the moon god at the temple in Ur. The destruction of the Ehulhul in Harran appears to be of great concern to Adad-guppi, and the gods respond to her pleas with a promise that the temple and city would be restored to a beauty surpassing their former glory. Nabonidus apparently carried out reconstruction but did not complete the temple until after Adad-guppi's death. The fragmentary end of the inscription details Adad-guppi's burial and funerary procession, including particulars about being interred with garments and a mantle of gold and precious stones. Nabonidus

slaughtered a sheep as part of the ritual for his deceased mother and ordered people throughout the empire to mourn for seven days, casting their clothes and cutting their hair. Mourners were then anointed with fine perfume and rejoiced as they went back to their homes. The inscription asserts that piety in one's worldly life will keep one's descendants safe and privileged, and Adad-guppi and her son Nabonidus were exemplars of such piety.

Date Range: 649 BCE - 539 BCE

Region: Harran, Turkey

Region tags: Asia, Syria, Turkey, Anatolia

The ancient city of Harran is located in modern-day southern Turkey near Sanliurfa near the Syrian border.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gadd, Cyril John. "The Harran Inscriptions of Nabonidus." *Anatolian Studies* (1958): 35-92.
- Source 2: Studevent-Hickman, Benjamin, Sarah C. Melville, and Scott Noegel, 2007. "Neo-Babylonian Period Texts from Babylonia and Syro-Palestine" in *The ancient Near East : historical sources in translation* ed. by Mark William Chavalas. Blackwell. Pg. 389-393
- Source 3: Breaulieu, Paul-Alain, 1989. *The Reign of Nabonidus King of Babylon*. Yale University Press.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.bibliotecapleyades.net/sitchin/adda_guppi_harran.htm
- Source 1 Description: Translations of Harran inscriptions
- Source 1 URL: https://faculty.uml.edu/ethan_spanier/teaching/documents/11.2neo-babyloniantexts.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Studevent-Hickman, Benjamin, Sarah C. Melville, and Scott Noegel, 2007. "Neo-Babylonian Period Texts from Babylonia and Syro-Palestine" in *The ancient Near East : historical sources in translation* ed. by Mark William Chavalas. Blackwell. Pg. 389-393
- Source 2 URL: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/129703513.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: Yun, S., 2017. Mother of her son: The literary scheme of the Adad-guppi Stele. *Acta Orientalia Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae*, 70(3), pp.277-294.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.scribd.com/document/519258619/Adad-Guppi>
- Source 1 Description: Weiershäuser, Frauke, and Jamie Novotny. *The Royal Inscriptions of Amēl-Marduk*

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

– Chisel

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Stone

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb

– No

Cemetery

– No

Temple

– Yes

- ↳ Shrine
 - No
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - No
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: One copy found in ancient temple in the archaeological ruins of Harran, other found in secondary use at the Great Mosque of Harran

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– I don't know

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– I don't know

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– I don't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: Written in Neo-Babylonian Akkadian. Questions arise as to whether or not this language was spoken or understood by a large population. This could be the language of the palace while the common language was Aramaic at this time.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

- ↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Written in Neo-Babylonian, which is a late form of Akkadian heavily influenced by Aramaic.

- ↳ Possess its own distinct written language?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Neo-Babylonian signs are distinct from other dialects of Akkadian

- ↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?
 - No

- ↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?
 - [Select all that apply]
 - Other [specify]: not known

- ↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?
 - No

- ↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?
 - Field doesn't know

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
 This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
 – Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?
 – I don't know

Are there clear reformist movements?
 (Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to

the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Worship of the Moon God Sin is in contrast to worship of Marduk, the traditional chief deity of the Babylonian Empire

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– I don't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

Notes: Two texts but appear to be same version. One is more intact than the other

Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: One copy of the texts is more intact than the other

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Funerary rites

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– I don't know

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Supernatural forces

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Text describes offerings brought to the dead but does not specify afterlife

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other instensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– Yes

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

↳ Personal effects?

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– Yes

↳ Significant value? (Gold, jade, so forth)

– Yes

↳ Some value? (valuable, or useful objects)

– Yes

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic

activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Funeral procession and mourning ritual

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– Yes

Notes: One could argue that some of the kings in the texts and Adad Guppi were "heroes"

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Sin the moon god, Ningal, Nusgu, Sardununna

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The Mesopotamian Mood God Sin, also called Nanna in earlier Babylonian sources

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: Emotions of humans: anger.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: Desires piety from followers

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: Moon God

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– No

↳ In dreams
– No

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?
– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?
– No

- ↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?
 - No
- ↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).
 - No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: It is the moon god, so presumably the moon represents the deity

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: This is a text about political leadership, so it focuses on the domain of kingship and royalty

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

Notes: It's not clear, but the text deals specifically with Harran and the kings of Babylon

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not clear from the text

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: Text suggests the gods could see Adad Cuppi and the Babylonian kings

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not clear in the text

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not clear in the text

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: While it seems they have knowledge of one another, they do not communicate explicitly

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: The text stresses that they reward humans based on their pious acts toward the gods and kings

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Notes: This is not specified in the text, but we know from other Mesopotamian sources that his parents are the gods Enlil and Ninlil, his consort is Ningal, and his children include Inanna/Ishtar and Utu/Shamash

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: While the moon god Sin is not considered the supreme god of Babylon, it is in this text and other texts from the time of Nabonidus

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– No

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Presence is marked by peace and stability in the city of Harran. Absence is marked by warfare and destruction

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: piety, service to kings, and veneration of deceased kings

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

Notes: the moon god sin leaves the city unprotected

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

Notes: While the text does not specify, we know from other historical sources that the city of Harran was destroyed in a battle for power between the Assyrians and their allies and the Babylonians and their allies

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: Sin the moon god leaves the temple and city of Harran because of non-observance, leaving it vulnerable for attack. He also presumably punishes the next in line for the throne because of their non-observance of ritual

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not clear from the text, which focuses more on the benefits of worshipping the Moon God during one's lifetime.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Other

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

Notes: While this does happen in other Mesopotamian texts, it is not specified in this text.

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

Notes: While this does happen in other Mesopotamian texts, it is not specified in this text.

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

Notes: While this does happen in other Mesopotamian texts, it is not specified in this text.

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Loss of rightful kingship to another more pious person

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

Notes: It seems that all the gods can bestow gifts on humans, but Sin is the supreme deity

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

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- ↳ Highly emphasized?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - No
 - Notes: Not specified in this text
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: Political success for ancestors

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - No
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– No

↳ Strength (physical)
– No

↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty
– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No

↳ Optimism/hope
– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Notes: Pleading to the gods in this text entails wearing a torn sackcloth and not wearing fine clothing, jewelry, or perfume.

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– No

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: n/a

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Text was not destroyed, but it has deteriorated due to age and poor preservation.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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